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BILATERAL DIFFUSE UVEAL MELANOCYTIC PROLIFERATION IN A PATIENT WITH NEWLY DIAGNOSED LEUKEMIA: A RARE CASE AND REVIEW OF MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES

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To report a rare case of bilateral diffuse uveal melanocytic proliferation (BDUMP) in a 64-year-old man with newly diagnosed leukemia, along with a review of the literature on the association between BDUMP and systemic malignancies.

A 64-year-old male presented with progressive vision loss in both eyes and was subsequently diagnosed with BDUMP, a rare paraneoplastic syndrome. The patient had recently been diagnosed with leukemia, which was found to be associated with his ocular condition. Fundoscopic examination revealed bilateral pigmented choroidal lesions, serous retinal detachment, and diffuse thickening of the uveal tract. Further diagnostic imaging, including B-scan ultrasonography and fluorescein angiography, confirmed the characteristic findings of BDUMP. Despite treatment for leukemia, the patient's ocular symptoms progressed, leading to significant visual impairment.

BDUMP is an extremely rare paraneoplastic phenomenon, with fewer than 100 cases reported in the literature, most commonly associated with solid tumors like ovarian, lung, and pancreatic cancers. Hematological malignancies, such as leukemia, are even more rarely linked to BDUMP. While the exact pathophysiology remains unclear, tumor-derived factors are thought to stimulate melanocytic proliferation in the uveal tract. Treatments focus on managing the malignancy. Ocular therapies, such as corticosteroids and immunosuppressive agents, are generally ineffective at reversing vision loss. Photodynamic therapy or radiation may stabilize symptoms, though visual recovery remains poor, emphasizing the need for early diagnosis and multidisciplinary care.

This case underscores rare association of BDUMP with newly diagnosed leukemia. BDUMP often presents alongside systemic malignancies and can precede cancer diagnosis. Early detection is crucial for identifying malignancies. Multidisciplinary management, involving oncologists and ophthalmologists, is essential. Further research is required to understand BDUMP's pathophysiology and management in hematologic malignancies.